

PREDICTORS OF CARDIOVASCULAR COMPLICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE AFTER BYPASS SURGERY

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Summary. in patients with chronic coronary heart disease (CHD) who underwent surgical myocardial revascularization, in the course of long-term prospective follow-up, to identify independent predictors of the development of fatal and non-fatal cardiovascular complications.

Material and methods. The study included 137 patients with coronary artery disease who underwent coronary artery bypass grafting under cardiopulmonary bypass. At follow-up for 2-5 years, deaths due to cardiac causes were recorded, including cases of sudden death, as well as the development of non-fatal cardiovascular complications (myocardial infarction, stroke).

Results and discussions. The mean duration of follow-up was 36 ± 3 months. During the observation period, 18 patients died: 9 due to myocardial infarction, 5 died suddenly, 3 patients died due to pneumonia. Of the non-fatal complications, myocardial infarction was registered in 5 cases, acute cerebrovascular accident - in 3 cases.

According to stepwise regression analysis, the following indicators were independent predictors of fatal cardiac complications:

- 1) ejection fraction less than 40% (relative risk - 5.7 with deviations within the 95% confidence interval 1.2–10.7);
- 2) age of patients 70 years and older (4.9; 1.4–8.4);
- 3) diabetes mellitus (2.3; 1.1–3.7);
- 4) left ventricular aneurysm (2.1; 1.04–3.8);
- 5) the duration of artificial lung ventilation for more than 24 hours (2.0; 1.2–2.9);
- 6) chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (1.9; 1.1–3.1).

Independent predictors of all cases of cardiovascular complications (both fatal and non-fatal) were:

- 1) age of patients 70 years and older (4.1; 1.2–8.1);
- 2) ejection fraction less than 40% (3.7; 1.1–6.5);
- 3) endarterectomy during coronary bypass surgery (2.9; 1.1–5.4);
- 4) duration of cardiopulmonary bypass over 100 minutes (2.2; 1.2–3.9); damage to the arteries of the brachiocephalic zone (2.1; 1.1–6.4); previous stroke (1.8; 1.1–3.8).

Conclusion. The study showed the importance of both traditional for IHD factors of unfavorable prognosis and comorbid pathology, features of surgical intervention and anesthetic management in the development of subsequent fatal and non-fatal cardiovascular complications in patients with chronic IHD who underwent surgical myocardial revascularization. Key words: ischemic heart disease, coronary artery bypass grafting, prognosis, cardiovascular complications.

References:

1. Shmueli H., Shah M., Ebinger JE, Nguyen LC, Chernomordik F., Flint N. et al. Left ventricular global longitudinal strain in identifying subclinical myocardial dysfunction among patients hospitalized with COVID-19. *Int. J. Cardiol. Heart Vasc.* 2021;32:100719. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijcha.2021.100719.
2. Wibowo A.,Pranata R., Astuti A., Tiksnadi V.V., Martanto E., Martha JW et al. Left and right ventricular longitudinal strains are associated with poor outcome in COVID-19: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J. Intensive Care.* 2021;9(1):9. DOI: 10.1186/s40560-020-00519-3.
3. Ахмедов А.Т., Особенности иммунной системы при врожденных пороках сердца, // EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. Vol. 2 No. 3 EJMP. – С. 35-40. [Akhmedov A. T., Features of the immune system in congenital heart defects, // EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. Vol. 2 no. 3 EJMP. – pp. 35-40 [in Russian]
4. Ахмедов А.Т., Сравнительная оценка иммунологических параметров лабораторных животных аутоимплантации тимуса в динамике наблюдения, // EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. - Vol. 2 No. 3: EJMP. С. 40-45 [Akhmedov A. T., Comparative evaluation of the immunological parameters of laboratory animals after thymus autoimplantation in the dynamics of observation, // EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. - 2022. - Vol. 2 no. 3: EJMP. С. 40-45 in Russian]

5. Sh, Navruzova, and A.T. Akhmedov. "Autoimplantation Of Thymus In Surgical Correction Of Congenital Heart Defects." *Central Asian Journal Of Medical And Natural Sciences* 2.3 (2021): 88-98.
6. Хидоятлов, Б. А. Микроциркуляторное русло кишечника и поджелудочной железы и его особенности при экспериментальном сахарном диабете / Б. А. Хидоятлов, А. Т. Ахмедов // *Морфология*. – 2008. – Т. 133. – № 2. – С. 145-146. – EDN JUTXTT.7. Otto CM, Pearlman AS Textbook of clinical echocardiography. Philadelphia: WB Saunders Co.; 1995:418.
7. Baumann R. et al. Definition for a common standard for 2D speckle tracking echocardiography: a consensus document of the EACVI/ASE/Industry Task Force to standardize deformation imaging. *Eur. Heart J. Cardiovasc. Imaging*. 2015;16(1):1-11. DOI: 10.1093/ehjci/jeu184.
8. Akhmedov A.T. (2022). COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF IMMUNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF LABORATORY ANIMALS WITH THYMUS AUTOIMPLANTATION IN THE DYNAMICS OF OBSERVATION. *International Journal of Medical Sciences And Clinical Research*, 2(11), 12-18. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijmscr/Volume02Issue11-03>
9. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). GENDER DIFFERENTIATION OF MASCULINE AND FEMININE VERBALIZATION. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(05), 59-65.
10. Djalilova, Z. O. (2021). Studies on gender linguistics in the field of Uzbek language. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(3), 391-397.
11. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). Physical activity and its impact on human health and longevity. *Достижения науки и образования*, (2 (82)), 120-126.
12. Obidovna, D. Z., & Denis, S. (2021). Formulas of speech etiquette in a gender-engineered communication strategy. *Central asian journal of theoretical & applied sciences*, 2(6), 5-11.
13. Obidovna, D. Z. (2021). Comparative Analysis Of Uzbek Men's And Women's Speech Through The Prism Of Gender Linguistics. *Central Asian journal of literature, philosophy and culture*, 2(2), 22-26.
14. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). Speech Behavior and its Gender Specificity on the Basis of the Main English Language Variants. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 22, 199-205.
15. Obidovna, D. Z. (2021). Gender issues in foreign theoretical linguistics: concerning the history of the issue. *Gender issues*, 7(6).

16. JALILOVA, Z. O. (2021, March). ON THE FORMATION OF THE LANGUAGE OF SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE IN THE HISTORY OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 18-22).
17. Jalilova, Z. O. (2020). Concerning the issue of terms, having a place with various morphological classes (in view of the example of the terminological arrangement of social action). *Новый день в медицине*, (4), 501-503.
18. Djalilova, Z. O., Juraev, S. S., & Kosimov, S. M. (2021). LATIN AS A PROFESSIONAL LANGUAGE OF MEDICAL WORKERS. *Международный научно-практический электронный журнал «МОЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ КАРЬЕРА»*. Выпуск № 23 (том 1)(апрель, 2021). Дата выхода в свет: 30.04. 2021., 79.
19. Джалилова, З. О., Хасанов, К. А., & Султонов, А. А. (2021). Роль научного управления в процессе обучения высококвалифицированных врачей в новом Узбекистане. *Молодой ученый*, (26), 377-379.
20. Dzhalilova, Z. O. (2021). The Latin language's international status. *Молодой ученый*, (41), 32-34.
21. Dzhalilova, Z. O., & Mirfajziev, K. (2021). Latin as the language of medicine. *Молодой ученый*, (41), 35-37.
22. Dzhalilova, Z. O., Izomova, S. G., & Ahmedova, G. A. (2021). Intercultural communication and the Latin language. *Молодой ученый*, (24), 398-400.
23. Dzhalilova, Z. O. (2021). History of formation of Latin language. *Молодой ученый*, (41), 34-35.
24. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). GENDER SPEECH BEHAVIOR IN THE CONTEXT OF THE SOCIO-LINGUISTIC FACTOR. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(6), 190-198.
25. Dzhalilova, Z. O., Hajdarova, N. S., & Tashpulatova, N. A. (2021). Latin in the Contemporary World. *Молодой ученый*, (24), 400-402.
26. Djalilova, Z. (2022). POLITENESS IN WOMEN'S DISCOURSE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Academic research in modern science*, 1(11), 29-34.
27. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). THE CONCEPT OF "HEALTHY LIFESTYLE" IN PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 3(06), 53-64.
28. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). A Speech Etiquette Formula for the Gender Communication Strategy. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(10), 44-50.
29. Djalilova, Z. (2022). DISCURSIVE ELEMENTS AND THE CATEGORY OF POLITENESS. *Academic research in modern science*, 1(12), 8-14.

30. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF MALE AND FEMALE ORAL SPEECH IN MODERN ENGLISH. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 2(10), 14-21.
31. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). THE MAIN CONCEPTS OF POLITENESS IN MODERN LINGUOPRAGMATICS: THE POLITENESS PRINCIPLE BY J. LEECH. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 2(11), 15-20.
32. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER DIFFERENTIATION OF DISCOURSE ELEMENTS AS INDICATORS OF POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE EVALUATIONS. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 2(12), 55-63.
33. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER-DETERMINED DIFFERENCES IN THE SPEECH OF LITERARY CHARACTERS. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(12), 210-215.
34. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER ELEMENT OF SPEECH BEHAVIOR FROM THE POSITION OF TEXT ORGANIZATION MECHANISMS. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(13), 274-281.
35. Джалилова, З. (2022). ПРАГМАТИЧЕСКИЙ ВЗГЛЯД НА МЕЖЛИЧНОСТНОЕ ОБЩЕНИЕ. *Zamonaviy dunyoda ilm-fan va texnologiya*, 1(7), 331-336.
- 36.
37. Djalilova, Z. O. (2023). A DISCOURSIIVE TURN IN THE THEORY OF LINGUISTIC POLITENESS: TO THE FORMATION OF THE THEORY OF LINGUISTIC IMPOLITENESS. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(02), 15-23.
38. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaimonovich, D. S. (2023). Influence of the Mode of Work and Recreation of the Student's Health. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH SYSTEMS AND MEDICAL SCIENCES*, 2(3), 3-5.
39. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2023). Forming a Healthy Lifestyle for Students on the Example of the Volleyball Section in Universities. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 3(3), 22-25.
40. Jo'rayev, S., & Djalilova, Z. (2022). NEUROLOGICAL STATUS OF CHILDREN WITH INTRAUTERINE DEVELOPMENTAL DELAY. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 2(9), 34-37.

